

Kinetics of Oxidation of Naphthols by Bromate and Iodate

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Manuscript received 23 July 1980, accepted 13 April 1981

The oxidation of α - and β -naphthols by bromate and iodate in aqueous acetic acid medium have been investigated. A first order dependence of rate on [substrate] and [oxidant] has been observed in both the cases. With both the oxidants the reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions and the order with respect to $[H^+]$ is fractional in the range of $[H_2SO_4]$ studied. The rate increases with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. Evidence for stable complex formation was obtained from Michael Menton's plot in the case of bromate. 1,2-Naphthoquinone has been reported to be the product in both the cases. A possible mechanism consistent with these observations has been proposed and the order of reactivity of IO_3^- and BrO_3^- has been discussed.

BROMATE and iodate act as oxidizing agents in acid medium with oxidation potentials of 1.44 V and 1.09 V. Literature survey shows that there are very few references of oxidation of naphthols and also the literature on oxidation by iodate is very limited. So this prompted us to investigate the comparative study of kinetics of oxidation of α - and β -naphthols by iodate and bromate.

Experimental

Materials and Methods: Potassium bromate, potassium iodate, acetic acid and sulphuric acid used were of BDH AnalaR grade. α and β -naphthols were recrystallized by normal procedure. Acetic acid was distilled by usual method. The reaction was studied under pseudo-first order conditions and the course of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted oxidant iodometrically.

Results and Discussion

Effect of [oxidant]: The reaction was studied with various oxidant concentrations under pseudo-first order conditions. The plot of \log (initial rate) versus \log [oxidant] was linear in both the cases and the slopes were approximately unity indicating first order dependence of rate on oxidant concentration in (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [OXIDANT] ON OXIDATION OF NAPHTHOLS

		$[H_2SO_4]=0.05M$; Acetic acid=40%; temp=30°			
Oxidant	Substrate	$k \times 10^3 (\text{lit. mol}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1})$ at $[BrO_3^-] \times 10^3 / M$			
		2.5	5.0	7.5	10.0
Bromate	α -Naphthol	10.3	10.26	10.28	10.28
	β -Naphthol	8.5	8.53	8.54	8.60
		$[H_2SO_4]=0.0M$; Acetic acid=50%; temp=10°			
		$k \times 10^3 (\text{lit. mol}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1})$ at $[IO_3^-] \times 10^3 / M$			
		1.0	2.0	4.0	8.0
Iodate	β -Naphthol	3.89	3.89	3.93	3.72

Effect of [substrate]: The reaction was followed at various substrate concentrations and when $\log k_{obs}$ versus \log [sub] was plotted linear plots were obtained in both the cases showing that the reaction is first order with respect to [substrate]. The Michael Menton's plot gave a positive intercept in the case of bromate oxidation suggesting the formation of a stable complex between the bromate ion and the naphthol, whereas in the case of iodate Michael Menton's plot did not give intercept indicating that the complex is not stable (Fig. 1).

Effect of $[H^+]$: In order to study the effect of hydrogen ion concentration, experiments were conducted at various sulphuric acid concentrations and the rate constants were determined. From a plot

Fig. 1. Michael Menton's Plot
(A) Oxidation of α -naphthol by bromate. $[BrO_3^-]=5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4]=0.05 M$, Acetic acid = 40%, temp. = 30°.
(B) Oxidation of β -naphthol by iodate. $[IO_3^-]=2 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4]=0.0 M$, Acetic acid=50% temp. = 10°.

of log k_{obs} versus log $[H^+]$ it has been concluded that the rate increases with increase in hydrogen ion concentration and it is fractional order with respect to $[H^+]$.

Effect of solvent : In order to study the effect of dielectric constant of the medium on the title reaction, the second order rate constants were determined in binary solvent mixtures (v/v) of acetic acid and water. The results are shown in Table 2. The rate increased on decreasing the

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SOLVENT ON OXIDATION OF NAPHTHOL^c BY BROMATE AND IODATE

$[BrO_3^-] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[Naphthol] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[IO_3^-] = 2 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[H_2SO_4] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$; temp = 30°

Oxidant	Substrate	$k \times 10^3$ lit.mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ at % HOAC				
		30%	40%	50%	60%	70%
Bromate	α -Naphthol	5.54	10.26	14.24	32.05	—
	β -Naphthol	4.80	8.58	13.96	27.92	—
Iodate*	α -Naphthol**	—	47.70	64.40	92.80	166.70
	β -Naphthol	—	31.28	42.70	69.50	139.10

* At $[H_2SO_4] = 0.0M$

** At temp = 10°

dielectric constant of the medium. The plot of log k_{II} versus $1/D$ gave a straight line with positive slope indicating the possibility of a reaction which may be either ion type or ion-dipole type. However, study of the reaction at various ionic strengths indicated that there is very little effect of ionic strength on the rate of reaction and thus rules out the possibility of ion-ion type of reaction.

Effect of temperature : The pseudo-first order rate constants were determined at various temperatures and the activation parameters are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF NAPHTHOLS BY BROMATE AND IODATE

$[BrO_3^-] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$; temp = 30°; $[H_2SO_4] = 0.05 M$;

$[Naphthol] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$; HOAC = 50%

Oxidant	Substrate	$k \times 10^3$ litres mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	ΔE	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
			K. Joules mol ⁻¹	Joules mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	K. Joules mol ⁻¹
Bromate	α -Naphthol	1.42	63.21	-79.87	84.89
	β -Naphthol	1.39	51.08	-120.09	84.93
Iodate	α -Naphthol*	28.78	61.99	-60.02	77.36
	β -Naphthol*	4.27	78.75	-5.61	76.65

* $[H_2SO_4] = 0.0M$; $[Naphthol] = 2 \times 10^{-3} M$

Product analysis : The product analysis shows that in both the cases α and β -naphthols yield 1,2-naphthoquinones as oxidation products. The product has been identified by condensing it with

orthophenylenediamine and comparing the melting point of the derivative with the literature value¹.

Stoichiometry : Reaction mixtures containing excess of the oxidant over naphthol were kept at room temperature in presence of sulphuric acid (0.05M) for 24 hrs. Estimation of the unreacted oxidant showed that three moles of naphthol consume two moles of oxidant. Therefore the reaction can be represented as :

The halide ion has been identified by usual methods. Taking all these observations into consideration the mechanism was proposed as in Scheme 1, and the rate expressions obtained in the

Scheme 1

case of bromate and iodate are given in equation 1 and 2 respectively.

$$-\frac{d[BrO_3^-]_T}{dt} = \frac{K_1 K_\alpha k_2 [BrO_3^-]_T [\text{substrate}] [H^+]^2}{1 + K_1 K_\alpha [\text{substrate}] + K_1 [H^+]^2} \dots (1)$$

$$-\frac{d[IO_3^-]_T}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_3 [IO_3^-]_T [\text{substrate}] [H^+]^2}{1 + K_1 [H^+]^2} \dots (2)$$

Under identical conditions phenol yields 1,2-quinone as the oxidation product in its oxidation by iodate and bromate². Naphthols undergo oxidation more rapidly than do phenols. Under identical conditions the rate constants for phenol and β -naphthol were 4.3×10^{-3} lit.mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹ and 59.0×10^{-3} lit.mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹ in the case of bromate oxidation.

When we used iodate as an oxidising agent the rate constants obtained were 2.24×10^{-2} lit.mol⁻¹sec⁻¹ and 143.1×10^{-2} lit.mol⁻¹sec⁻¹ respectively under identical conditions. Thus indicating that with bromate the rate increased 15 times from phenol to naphthol and with iodate it is 70 times faster with naphthol. This higher reactivity is due to the fact that the naphthalene ring is stabilized by resonance to a larger extent compared to benzene ring.

Of the two naphthols α -naphthol reacts faster than β -naphthol both with bromate and iodate as oxidising agents. In the case of α -naphthol the attack of oxidant at the α -position yields intermediate carbonium ion that is a hybrid of two structures (I and II) which accommodate the charge on the same ring under attack, whereas in β -naphthol only one structure(III) is possible for the carbonium ion. Therefore in α -naphthol the stabilization of the carbonium ion occurs more effectively than in β -naphthol³. Hence one would expect that the oxidation of α -naphthol occurs more rapidly than that of β -naphthol.

Of the two oxidants iodate reacts more readily than bromate. The rate constant for the oxidation

of β -naphthol in 50% (v/v) acetic acid water mixture in presence of 0.05M sulphuric acid at 30° is 9.88×10^{-2} lit.mol⁻¹sec⁻¹. Under identical conditions for bromate oxidation it is 1.4×10^{-2} lit.mol⁻¹sec⁻¹. This difference in rates is attributed to the difference in strengths of O-I and O-Br bonds formed in the oxidant-substrate complex. Since O-I bond is weaker than O-Br bond it is readily broken during the decomposition of the complex. This is also evident from the Michael Menton's plot. In the case of bromate oxidation we obtained a positive intercept suggesting that the complex is stable and decomposes in a slow step, whereas with iodate there was no intercept indicating that the complex is not stable. It was also observed that there is no correlation between the oxidation potential and the rate of oxidation.

References

1. J. R. A. POLLOCK and R. STEVENS, 'Dictionary of Organic Compounds', Eyre-Spottis Woode, Publishers, London, 1965, 348.
2. VIJAYALAKSHMI and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 612.
3. R. T. MARRISON and R. N. BOYD, 'Organic Chemistry', Prentice Hall, New Delhi, 1971, 1049.